

The Effect of Green Marketing on Students' Selection of Private Universities in Jordan

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Abstract

This study attempts to explore the effect of green marketing on students' selection of private universities in Jordan. More companies are using green marketing as a sustainable competitive advantage, including private universities. This article is a pioneer attempt to explore the effect of green marketing on students' selection of private universities in Jordan. A questionnaire was used to measure the influence of environmental knowledge, university reputation, physical environment, and education quality on students' selection of private universities. Regarding data collection, about 650 usable questionnaires were collected from three private universities. Factor analysis, multiple and simple regression used to analyze the data. Results show that all variables have a significant effect on students' selection of private universities, while among the four, education quality emerged as the highest effect on students' selection. The findings show that universities can be successful in attaining their market objectives by initiating and adopting green marketing oriented activities.

Introduction

With the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic all over the world, the attitudes of consumers have changed regarding environmental issues. More attention is devoted to issues related to climate change, air pollution, and consumer health. Threatened by limited resources, an unstable economy, and slow growth, a lot of businesses took the initiative to implement green marketing to face increasing competition, attain more opportunities, and cut costs. Once the company wants to gain a sustainable competitive advantage, it must integrate environmental thinking into all aspects of marketing (Porter, 1998). Therefore, it is so critical for a private university to be market-oriented by initiating and adopting market-oriented activities to be successful in attaining their goals (Zebal and Goodwin, 2012). Universities are an influential change agent can be the best place to apply this strategic approach since they are involved in scientific research and development. Universities can be crucial vicinity in developing and upgrading new standards that protect the environment and enhance sustainability to support the university's green marketing strategy. In other words, applying green marketing standards and strategies will enable the university to manage changes in the internal and external environment more efficiently and effectively than its counterpart. Globalization and rapid technological advancement have changed the higher education landscape. The increase in the number of universities offering various educational services has led to a highly competitive market. To stay financially viable, private universities depend primarily on student enrollment that we can portray as the lifeblood of colleges and universities, as noted by Kinzie et al. (2004, p4). Marketing can be the hallmark for private universities if they want to succeed in this intense and competitive market. There is growing evidence showing that employing marketing activities have a direct influence on recruiting university students (Lang, 2009; Noel-Levitz, 2012). Green marketing can be a very supportive tool in higher education to achieve a competitive advantage by reaching the sustainable university stage.

In higher education, there are different existing classifications that rate and rank universities according to their environmental sustainability performance. For example, in 2010, *Universitas Indonesia* (UI) launched an initiative to create GreenMetric World University Ranking. The ranking aims to evaluate the current situation and policies with regards to sustainability and green campus in universities all over the world. The selected criteria for this ranking include very significant factors that pertain to sustainability. This ranking classified the universities based on six significant measures, which are: Setting and Infrastructure (SI), Energy and Climate Change (EC), Waste (WS), Water (WR), Transportation (TR) (UI proceeding, 2019). Apart from the increasing number of private universities

and students who are joining those universities in the Arab world, scant academic research was done on student selection in general and almost none about studying the effect of green marketing on students' selection of university. Explicitly, this study aims to examine the influence of environmental knowledge, physical environment, university reputation, and education quality on students' selection of private universities. The research objectives are to explore the level of environmental knowledge of students in a private university in Jordan and to examine if there is any effect for environmental knowledge, university reputation, the physical environment, and education quality on students' selection of private university in Amman - Jordan. This research will serve as a pioneering effort for other researchers to build on in the area of green marketing and its implications in higher education.

Literature Review

Green Marketing Development

Before we define what green marketing is, it is crucial to identify and understand how green marketing has evolved and why defined in this way. Historically, there are three well-known phases in green marketing development. From the 1960s, the first phase was concerned with ecological issues and focused on issues and problems, e.g. (Air & water pollution) created by industrial sectors and how it affects the environment, so it was named an ecological green marketing era. The second era started from 1980 till 1990, which witnessed the development and applying of new clean technology, innovations, and new sustainability policies for both manufacturers and service providers to attain a competitive advantage. Researchers labeled this stage with an environmental green marketing era, which is more comprehensive than the ecological green marketing era. The third era of development is sustainable green marketing started from 1990 until now. Kasilingam (2020) summarizes the main aims of green marketing as follows: make environmentalism profitable, bringing out product modifications, packaging changes, eliminate the concept of waste, make prices reflect actual and environmental costs, and reinvent the concept of a product and changes in production processes.

Green Marketing Definition

Academically and practically, the green marketing concept has been accepted to attain customers' needs and anticipation towards products and services in a beneficial and sustainable approach (Lin et al. 2017). The dynamic conception of Green marketing has covered different areas and activities inside and outside the domain of marketing. This diversity encouraged researchers from various fields to employ this concept in their research. The American marketing association defined green marketing "as the marketing of products that are believed to be environmentally friendly which organize into various activities such as product adjustment, modification of production processes, packaging, labeling, advertising strategies as well as increases awareness on compliance marketing among industries" (Porter, 1998).

Green University

The shift towards a green university has become a growing demand for all universities. Many universities are under pressure from students and governments to operate campuses in a more sustainable manner (Sharp, 2002). Moving towards this end is neither an easy task nor a straightforward process. To be able to overcome these barriers, the first step is to make sustainability explicit in the university academic and research policies, institutional mission, and planning (Hani Abu Qdais et al., 2019). It is crucial to integrate education with sustainable development goals sought by public and private universities. Since the role of the educational system is to improve the quality of life, we need to turn universities into sustainable institutions to contribute to the sustainable development of their communities. Velazquez et al. (2006) defined green education as the modern education that seeks sustainable development, keeping abreast of technological development and benefiting from it in all other elements of the educational process with high efficiency and outstanding products according to environmentally friendly standards. Green university operations embrace two broad areas. The first area is related to environmental programs of buildings, energy, forestry, and services, and this aspect is available in many universities in Arab Countries (Nguyen et al., 2019). The second area focuses on the educational process with the techniques, strategies, applications, and practices related to the concept of green education, and many countries have started to adopt it in their institutions and educational system (Grindsted, 2011).

Private Universities in Jordan and Green Marketing

Jordan has witnessed accelerated growth in all areas embracing higher education. More students were looking to join university, but public universities were unable to meet the students' demands. Consequently, the private University Act was passed in 1989, and the Ministry of higher education has granted the license for the first time for a private university to start admission from the academic year 89/90. The year 1990 witnessed the launching of the first private university in Jordan. Currently, the

number of licensed private universities reached 19 universities covering all fields of study programs except for medical studies. According to 2017/2018 statistics, the total number of undergraduate students in private universities were 67222 students (MOHE, 2018). In Jordan, the interest in green marketing varies from one university to another. It is evident from the sustainable projects and practices applied inside the university. The philosophy of a green university depends on designing activities to be accomplished sustainably. To achieve this goal, many private universities in Jordan took practical steps towards transferring the campus into an environment-friendly campus. A Green Campus is a place where environmental-friendly practices and education combine to promote sustainable and eco-friendly practices on the campus. Petra University is one of the most outstanding private universities in applying the green marketing concept. About 50% of the total area of the university is a natural area with 10,000 trees. The Policy aims to rehabilitate infrastructure and building architecture, a Free-smoking campus, Camera-controlled campus against abuse. The solar system also was installed on rooftops and parking lots to reduce the cost of electricity to zero in 2019.

According to the environmental sustainability report 2017/2018, Ahliyyah Amman University has dedicated about US\$ 2,769,850 for sustainability infrastructure and efforts, and more than 20,000 Meter Square area has been installed with Solar Panels to generated more than 1500 KW of electricity. The total numbers of courses with sustainability in (2018/2019) are 33 courses, p54. Another example is *Al-Zaytoonah* University of Jordan (ZUJ). Recently they carried out a large-scale sustainable energy project in an attempt to reduce its operational expenses. ZUJ has designed its strategic sustainability goals to develop its campus in efficient use of energy, water, and waste management. Also, ZUJ adopted an irrigation system that utilizes reclaimed water from its wastewater treatment plant. The university had also invested in energy-efficient light fixtures and smart appliances in the air conditioning and heating (Bazlamit et al., 2020).

Empirical Research

Academic research on higher education is considered a global phenomenon. One stream of research is about how students select the university and what factors may affect their decision. Most of the previous research focused on both personal factors and university factors. For example, Sidin et al. (2003) found that the campus environment, academic quality, facilities, and personal characteristics are significant criteria for students' selection. Hagel and Shaw (2008) found that location, academic reputation, tuition fees, and living costs as well as university facilities. Another study by Kusumawati et al. (2010) found that student's top five factors in the choice of universities were reputation, job prospects, lower cost, proximity, and parents' influence. While Soner Polat (2012) found that among different factors that affect student selection of university, the physical conditions of the university emerge as the most important factor, followed by cultural facilities and the informal information about the university. Yano et al. (2014) summarized that the main factors to affect the process of college selection at the University of Eldoret were education quality, job opportunities, institution reputation, campus location, and flexibility in the course requirements.

Awang (2015) studied eight variables related to students' decision-making. Three variables emerged as the most influential those variables were university reputation and ranked first, while the family support variable ranked second and employability after graduation ranked in third place. Krezel and Krezel (2017) examined several social choice models that influence the selection of higher education institutions. They classified social factors into three main categories: 1. Institutional factors; 2. Student-related characteristics; and 3. Social environment, i.e., the family and peers. Rahmat et al. (2018) study indicated that the cost of education, promotion, brand image, motivation, and facilities have a positive and significant effect on the decision of students to choose private universities in Medan, Indonesia. Another study by Connie et al. (2018) found that there is a positive relationship between university reputation, pricing, program, security, employment opportunity, and campus facilities, friends, location, and college choice.

Methods

To achieve the aims of this study, a structured questionnaire was employed to collect the required data. The researcher used a convenience sampling method to collect data from undergraduate students. The questionnaires were distributed randomly to students at three private universities in the city of Amman, Jordan. Permission was taken from faculty members to allow students to fill in the questionnaire inside

the class after given them a brief description of the nature of the study to avoid any mistakes while they answer. The questionnaire consists of two parts. The first part was about student demographics, while the second part was concerning the independent and dependent variables. Variables were measured in the proposed model by 34 questions included in the instrument. A five-point Likert scale ranging from (1=Strongly Disagree to 5=Strongly Agree) to capture the students' response. Items used to measure were adopted from existing literature as follows; University Reputation and Physical Environment, adopted from Connie et al. (2018) and Awang (2015). Education Quality questions were adopted from Hossain et al. (2018). While environmental knowledge questions were adopted from Pham (2019) and El Sakka (2016). A total of 750 questionnaires were distributed directly to students during the first semester from 12 till 30 of January 2020. About 679 questionnaires were filled and returned by students. After checking, the researcher found 29 uncompleted questionnaires. Hence, 650 questionnaires were usable and entered for data analysis (86% response rate).

Descriptive results show that majority of respondents were male students with 63.6 percent and female students were 36.4 percent. Since our target population is undergraduate students, the majority aged between 18-22 years old with 85.8 percent, while students aged between 23-26 were 12.5 percent, and the lowest percentage was for more than 27 years old with 1.7 percent. About 30 percent of the students were in the second year, followed by fourth and third year respectively with 28.8 and 22.5 percent. Finally, students from different colleges participate in filling in the questionnaire. Business students were the majority with 30.9 percent, followed by pharmacy 22.9 percent, law 21.1 percent, and Arts with 15.5 percent sequentially.

Analysis and Results

SPSS Version 22 was used to analyze and interpret data for this study. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) procedure was used for scale refinement. To extract factors, we used the component analysis technique, while for arriving at a rotated solution, The Varimax rotation technique was used (Hair et al. 2014). Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was high (0.827) and above the commonly recommended value of .65, and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was significant (χ^2 (496) = 5328.913, $p < .000$). Hence, factorability is assumed, it is deemed appropriate to proceed with factor analysis (Field, 2009).

According to Hair et al. (2014), only factors with Eigenvalues greater than 1.00 with a cumulative percentage above 50 percent and factor loading for each item loading 0.50 or greater are considered significant. Table 1 shows the result of Exploratory Factor Analysis, it reveals that one item from Physical Environment (PE3), and University Reputation (UR3) was dropped. Cronbach's alpha values for these constructs were 0.729, 0.738, 0.767, 0.709, and 0.702, respectively, and hence it passes the 0.7 thresholds as indicated by Hair et al. (2014), approving acceptable reliability of the measurement model.

Table1: Exploratory Factor Analysis

Constructs	Items	Mean	SD	Standardized Factor Loadings	Cronbach's alpha
EK1		3.19	1.281	0.635	72.9
EK2		3.09	1.287	0.752	
EK3		3.14	1.375	0.630	
EK4		3.82	1.255	0.823	
EK5		3.48	1.208	0.790	
EK6		3.95	1.059	0.630	
PE1		3.70	1.145	0.689	73.8
PE2		3.76	1.090	0.678	
PE3		3.56	1.172	0.477	
PE4		3.89	1.131	0.545	
PE5		3.46	1.194	0.605	
PE6		3.72	1.251	0.720	
PE7		3.77	1.085	0.642	
PE8		4.09	1.009	0.740	
UR1		3.52	1.385	0.659	76.7
UR2		3.17	1.272	0.549	
UR3		3.72	1.134	0.487	
UR4		3.39	1.287	0.767	
UR5		3.00	1.432	0.685	
UR6		3.83	1.181	0.631	

EQ1	3.92	1.201	0.541	
EQ2	3.99	1.000	0.586	
EQ3	3.54	1.243	0.729	70.9
EQ4	3.64	1.202	0.755	
EQ5	3.57	1.296	0.720	
EQ6	4.23	.945	0.476	
SS1	3.88	1.175	0.585	
SS2	3.34	1.373	0.882	
SS3	3.28	1.249	0.860	70.2
SS4	3.97	1.075	0.710	
SS5	3.28	1.424	0.489	
SS6	3.96	1.124	0.732	
Total explained variance (.671)				
Varimax rotation				

Research Model

Based on the results obtained from the Exploratory Factor Analysis, we propose a research model for this study presented in figure 1. The model consists of four independent variables 1) Environmental knowledge, 2) Physical Environment, 3) University Reputation and, 4) Education Quality. Those variables are expected to have a significant effect on students’ selection of private universities.

Figure 1: Research Model

Research Hypotheses

Based on the above research model, the following hypotheses are suggested:

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant effect of green marketing variables (environmental knowledge, physical environment, university reputation, and education quality) on students’ selection of private universities at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

To identify the effect of each green Marketing Variables on students’ selection of private universities, the researcher split this hypothesis into four sub-hypotheses and uses the simple regression analysis to test each sub-hypothesis, as a follows:

Hypothesis 1.1: There is a significant effect of Physical Environment on students’ selection of private universities.

Hypothesis 1.2: There is a significant effect of University Reputation on students’ selection of private universities.

Hypothesis 1.3: There is a significant effect of Environmental knowledge on students’ selection of private universities.

Hypothesis 1.4: There is a significant effect of Education Quality on students’ selection of private universities.

Hypotheses Testing

To test the research main hypotheses, multiple regression analysis was conducted. Multiple regressions identify each variable’s relative contribution and determine the best predictor variable between a set of variables (Hair et al., 2014). Results shown in Table 2 indicate that there is a significant effect of environmental knowledge, physical environment, university reputation, and education quality students’ selection of private universities. The R was (0.556) at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), whereas the R^2 was (0.309). This means the (30.9) of student selection changeability’s results from the changeability in the green marketing variables. ANOVA test shows that the significant impacts F calculate was (72.242) and its significance at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), and based on that, we accept the main hypothesis.

Table 2: Results of Regression analysis

Coefficients^a						
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	2.094	.225		9.299	.000
	PE	.093	.047	.070	1.979	.048
	UR	-.098-	.037	-.110-	-2.618-	.009
	EK	-.129-	.040	-.133-	-3.238-	.001
	EQ	.513	.036	.480	14.365	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Student selection

Results of Simple Regression analysis for four sub-hypothesis are presented in Table 3. Results show that there is no significant effect for the physical environment on students' selection, and the R^2 obtained is weak. University reputation and environmental knowledge got a higher R^2 than the physical environment but still considered a weak effect on students' selection despite having significance at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) level. The highest R^2 obtained in this analysis was for education quality with a very high F significance at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) level. This result can give us more insight into what variables have more effect on students' selection of a private university. As shown in Table 3, education quality can be the core of private university orientation in applying a green marketing strategy.

Table 3: Results of Simple Regression analysis

hypotheses	R	R Square	F	Sig	Result
H1.1 PE SS	.028	.010	.376	.540	Rejected
H1.2 UR SS	.232	.054	37.005	.000	Accepted
H1.3 EK SS	.247	.061	41.932	.000	Accepted
H1.4 EQ SS	.519	.270	239.384	.000	Accepted

Discussion and Recommendations

In this article, we embark on a new area of research by shedding light on the effect of green marketing use on students' selection of private universities. Most of the research done on students' selection was concerned with variables other than green marketing. This research is a pioneer in tackling this topic in Jordan. The research aims to examine the effect of green marketing on students' selection of private universities in Jordan. Factor analysis results created four variables; environmental knowledge, physical environment, education quality, and university reputation. The regression model was significant, and all variables were significant. Education quality reveals as the most important variable for students, and this result is in line with the results of (Hossain 2018). While in simple regression, the physical environment was not significant. The reason behind this can be that environmental activities such as water recycling are not clear for students. It is recommended that universities plead with green building design and increase green areas inside the campus. It will give the student a positive impression and make him more aware of environmental projects and activities. Also, universities need to carry out green marketing campaigns via social media and other tools to inform students, parents, and stakeholders about the progress in green marketing projects. It will help the university in generating positive word of mouth and improve its reputation.

Results also show that university reputation plays a very crucial role in students' selection since this will affect their future career and growth. Private universities recommended working very hard on national and international ranking to build a strong brand for itself in the local and international markets, and this result is similar to Awang (2018) and Ryan (2014). Student environmental knowledge also plays a central role in the success of university environmental initiatives. For example, it is critical to highlight the importance of recycling for water, paper, and other resources to maintain sustainability and limited resources by encouraging students to use online applications, uploading e-documents, use categorized trash bins and bicycles inside the campus. Also, keep and maintain a healthy atmosphere by emphasizing a smoke-free campus. Finally, results show that quality education has the highest effect on students' selection. Universities need to leverage the quality of education by upgrading and introducing a new curriculum to equip students with modern skills, information, experience, and values to meet the competitive market requirements. Different faculties can incorporate environmental issues in their curriculum, such as green marketing, HR and sustainability, faculty of engineering by focusing on renewable energy, faculty of law, and how to enforce rules and regulations concerning all aspects of environmental sustainability. Finally, students and parents need to feel that they are getting back high education quality for whatever they are paying to a private university. This result is in line with Hossain (2018) and Semsia (2018).

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